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Research Article

MOUTHGUARDS FOR SPORTSMEN WHO GO IN FOR CONTACT SPORTS

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Abstract

The article describes statistics of traumas of sportsmen who go in for contact sports. Sports are listed in which the protective dental splints must be used as devices for prevention of traumas of maxillofacial region. Advantages of the individual protective dental splint are determined which is manufactured by thermoforming from several layers of a constructional material. Characteristics and advices are given for use of individual protective dental splints in various sports.

Key Words: *prevention of sports injury, individual protective dental splints, ethylene-vinyl acetate.*

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INTRODUCTION:

This work was done at Sechenov University with supported by the "Russian Academic Excellence Project 5-100". The issue of this article will be individual protective dental splints as modern devices for prevention of trauma of maxillofacial region in sportsmen. Such prevention measures are particularly important for persons who go in for contact sports where confrontation of rivals often leads to serious traumas including traumas of maxillofacial region [1].

Results of researches, which were published by the Journal of the American Dental Association (JADA), showed that from 13 to 39% of all dental traumas had been received during sports activities. Men received traumas twice as frequently as women. And the most frequent dental traumas were injuries of a central incisor of upper jaw [2].

Data of the National Collegiate Athletic Association of the USA (NCAA) showed that in 2007 the maximum amount of traumas of orofacial region per 1000 competitions had been registered in the following sports: American football (35.9%), basketball (26.6%), wrestling (26.4%), football (18.8%), and ice hockey (16.3%). The above mentioned sports disciplines are considered to be high-injury ones because contestants directly contact equipment and outfit. Such sports as ice hockey have a higher probability of receiving the traumas not only from contact with a rival (13.5%) but also with rival's hockey stick (24.5%) or puck (19.1%). It must be noted that severity of received traumas is proportional to increase of load which the sportsmen undergo daily [3].

Topicality of the problem is confirmed also by researches which have been conducted by Russian doctors. Terenteva O.I. monitored traumatism in the ice-hockey team "Tractor" of the Russian Hockey League for 5 years; her research results revealed that each hockey player had received 22.06 ± 1.97 traumas. Altogether 2136 cases were recorded what amounted to 87.4% of all registered pathologies in the team. Contusions (68.4% of all traumas), wounds and scratches (21.8%) prevailed among traumas. As for localization of traumas, the most frequent ones were traumas of head and neck (18.5% of all traumas), hip (13.8%) and shin (8.9%). When analyzing the amount of traumas, their localization, character and severity in players of various specializations one must consider all factors which influence this process [4].

Causes of occurrence of sports injuries can be united into several groups. The following classification of causes of occurrence of sports injuries seems to be

advisable: mistakes in technique of training; violation of rules of organization of training and competitions; shortcomings of material and technical means for training and competitions; unfavorable meteorological and sanitary conditions during training and competitions; non-compliance with requirements of medical supervision, sportsmen' lack of discipline [5]. Irrespectively of a sportsman's skills and level of training, each participant in sports "games" must abide by basic safety rules and use available means of traumas prevention.

Protective dental splints are considered to be the most widespread means for prevention of traumas of dentofacial system. The protective dental splints are recommended for use for the following sports: acrobatics, basketball, box, field hockey, football, gymnastics, handball, ice hockey, lacrosse, martial arts, badminton, roller hockey, rugby, shot put, skateboarding, skiing, parachute jumps, squash rackets, surf-riding, volleyball, water polo, weightlifting, wrestling [6]. The individual protective dental splint is a device for prevention of trauma of dentofacial system; this device is manufactured from elastomeric or thermoplastic plastic and has some distinguishing characteristics and features with respect to teeth rows, forms of jaws and occlusion. They are subdivided into two main groups: standard ones and individual ones. Every individual protective dental splint will be several times more effective than its analogs which are standard half-finished products. It will secure higher values of the following parameters: level of protection, comfort and easiness of use, lifetime, possibility of use in combination with orthodontic and orthopedic constructions, absence of hindrance to speech and breathing; one of obvious advantages of such protective splint is increase in strength and endurance of a sportsman [7]. An individual dental splint is well fixed on upper jaw that allows to increase energy of impact dissipation and increase adaptation rate; moreover, there is no probability of aspiration of a foreign body into respiratory tracts. Individual protective dental splints not only help to prevent damages of a tooth, such as splits, destructions or a full loss of the tooth, they also secure protection of other organs and tissues. Protective dental splints can substantially reduce probability of occurrence of traumas of head, neck and oral cavity and reduce severity of these traumas. Such serious traumas as brain concussion, intracerebral bleedings, loss of consciousness, jaw fractures and injuries of neck are associated with situations where the lower jaw strikes against the upper one [8]. Easiness and comfort of use are connected with a differentiated approach to manufacturing of every splint, depending on a sport and anatomical traits. Every splint is employed by its user

individually and cannot be applied by another sportsman. It is determined not only by hygienic reasons but by anatomical distinctive features too.

Modern biopolymers, such as ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) allow to manufacture an individual protective dental splint according to all requirements and distinctive features of sportsmen, they allow to take into account their wishes too. It can be a color, emblem or flag of a team and even a level of protection [9-12].

The most important feature of such protective splints is their multilayer composition. Combination of ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) layers and laminate, which is manufactured on its basis, allow to distribute impact energy by 43% and increase flexural strength up to 22% as compared with a single-layered protective dental splint of the same thickness [5]. To choose an optimal construction it is advisable to subdivide individual protective dental splints according to level of protection and according to the sport for which the protective splint is recommended.

Light - the protective dental splint which has thickness of 4 mm and consists of 2 plates, each of 2 mm. It can be used in such sports as bicycling and motocross.

Medium - the protective dental splint which has thickness of 6 mm and consists of two plates, 2 mm and 4 mm. It can be used in such sports as acrobatics, basketball, field hockey, football, gymnastics, handball, ice hockey, lacrosse, badminton, roller hockey, rugby, shot put, parachute jumps, surf-riding, volleyball, water polo, weightlifting. This type of the protective splint is the most widespread one among sportsmen; it has a good level of protection and reasonable price [5].

Heavy - the protective dental splint which has thickness of 6 mm and consists of two plates 2 mm and 4 mm, it is combined with harder strips which are placed in the region of neck of tooth and cutting edge. Such combination allows to prevent traumas in the most vulnerable places, evenly distribute load on the whole surface of the protective splint and transfer the load to upper jaw, and at that the impact force is partially reduced. This splint can be used in such sports as box, cricket, wrestling, skateboarding, cross-country skiing, squash rackets [5].

Another variant, which has a similar construction, is the protective splint SuperHeavy, where hard interlayer is a layer of material on the basis of copolymer of butadiene and styrene which has thickness of 0.8 mm. The layer, which has thickness of 0.8 mm, fully covers anterior part of teeth, overlaps cutting edge and passes to inner

surface. Such splint allows to distribute load by 23.5% more effectively than Light. The protective splint, which meets all requirements for safety and comfort, can be manufactured by using materials of companies Dreve and ERKODENT. Innovative techniques allow to produce multi-layer individual protective dental splints having various forms, colors and strength [5].

Assortment of company Dreve includes several kinds of materials.

Drufosoftcolour is a material having thickness of 3 mm. One can choose a color (manufacturer offers 21 colors for choice). The material has a good adhesion between layers and allows to manufacture an individual protective splint having thickness up to 6 mm. It is possible to combine a colored layer and a transparent one with a logo of the team, to which a player belongs, or with the flag of a state. Such image is situated against background of a colored monochrome layer and is covered by a transparent one. The combination of the transparent layer with a monochrome one allows to obtain an optimal thickness of the individual protective dental splint.

DrufosoftcolourMix is a material having thickness of 3 mm. The package contains 25 plates of different colors. There are both monochrome plates and the ones which have three colors. They allow to use three-colored plates as a background and there is a possibility to cover them by a transparent layer. It helps considerably reduce time for manufacturing the protective splints with the basis having several colors.

Drufosoft-shell is a product in the form of half-finished protective splints. It allows to save time of thermoshaping the first layer of a splint. It is possible to use such half-finished products for manufacturing of protective splints directly during sporting events when time and conditions for manufacturing of splints are limited.

BIOLON are plates having thickness of 0.5 and 0.75 mm. When combined with plates having thickness of 2 and 3 mm, they allow to create a construction which meets requirements that are set for protective splints of the class SuperHeavy.

DrufosoftPrimer is a liquid primer which allows to increase adhesion between plates during manufacturing of a protective splint.

Assortment of company ERKODENT includes several kinds of materials. The half-finished products are either round (120 mm in diameter) or square (125x125 mm). Besides that, the company offers full range of tools

which allow to process an article during intermediate stages and process a finished product.

PLAYSAFE-Set 125x125 mm, 1farbig, heavy-pro consists of the transparent layer ERKOFLEX 2.0 mm, monochrome plate ERKOFLEX 4.0 mm and ERKODUR-S 0.8 mm.

PLAYSAFE-Set 125x125 mm, 1farbig, light consists of the transparent ERKOFLEX 2.0 mm and monochrome plate ERKOFLEX 2.0 mm.

PLAYSAFE-Set 125x125 mm, 1farbig, light-pro consists of the transparent ERKOFLEX 2.0 mm, monochrome plate ERKOFLEX 2.0 mm, ERKODUR-S 0.8 mm.

PLAYSAFE-Set 125x125 mm, 1farbig, medium consists of the transparent ERKOFLEX 2.0 mm, monochrome plate 1xERKOFLEX 4.0 mm.

All sets can be provided with both monochrome plates and with plates having two, three and four colors (2 and 4 mm).

In addition to half-finished protective splints having various colors, thickness and properties, the company offers equipment for manufacturing thereof. Every machine for production of protective splints has an automatic mode of pressure and temperature, depending on material; it also has a manual adjustment mode which is used if necessary.

CONCLUSION:

Stably high rate of traumas of maxillofacial region in sportsmen, who go in for contact sports, determines topicality of use of individual protective dental splints. Innovative technologies of employment of ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) allow to manufacture an individual protective dental splint according to all requirements and distinctive features of sportsmen and allow to use advantages of participation in competitions to the maximum and reduce risk of sportsmen' trauma.

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